

AI, Big Data & Democracy Task Force

Democracy, AI, Big Data

Taskforce Description

The AI, BIG DATA and DEMOCRACY TASK FORCE is a cluster composed of four different EU-funded projects supporting together the European Commission's commitment to supporting "Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies". While AI4Gov, KT4D and ITHACA are funded under the Horizon call 'Artificial intelligence, big data and democracy', ORBIS is funded under 'The future of democracy and civic participation'. Each Project provides a unique perspectives from different approaches and academic disciplines, but with a common goal as they are working to create solutions to foster and safeguard democracy and civic participation against risks and impacts stemming from AI and Big Data. The collaborative effort will result in furnishing policymakers and citizens with tools for evidence-based decision-making while utilising state-of-the-art developments in emerging Information Technologies while also taking into account vulnerable groups and cultural aspects.

The 2 Funding Calls

The call '**Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, and Democracy**' seeks to analyse AI and Big Data's societal impacts, ensuring citizen rights and civic participation. It focuses on regulations, bridging the gap between ethics and tech, data ownership, and transparency. Particular attention is given to vulnerable groups, innovative civic engagement, and citizens' education.

'**The Future of Democracy and Civic Participation**' call aims to create a European network. Projects provide policy recommendations, support policymakers, analyse participation, organise events, and raise awareness. The goal is global, aiming to link with similar initiatives worldwide, fostering democratic synergies.

The HRB - Horizon Result Booster is an initiative funded European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation, Unit J5, Common Service for Horizon 2020 Information and Data.

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Key Results

Key results from the projects will include:

Policy Briefs

Toolkits & tools

Platforms

Ethical Data Approaches

Governance Frameworks

The Impacts

The AI, Big Data, and Democracy Task Force, aims to integrate diverse approaches and disciplines to protect democracy and civic participation from AI and Big Data risks. Projects within the task force focus on addressing ethical concerns, enhancing civic participation, and ensuring transparent and inclusive decision-making processes. By organizing joint activities and leveraging a dissemination network, the task force aims to align interests while maintaining individual project goals. Ultimately, the projects aim to develop tools and methodologies for evidence-based decision-making, utilizing advancements in AI and Big Data while prioritizing the needs of vulnerable groups.

Challenges

Societal/Socio-Cultural

These projects aim to protect and sustain democracy while fostering citizen engagement through AI and Big Data solutions. They promote transparency and fairness in decision-making, considering ethical and societal factors. By sharing knowledge and advancing AI research, the projects contribute to Europe's leadership in innovation.

Scientific & Technological

The taskforce explores how AI and Big Data impact democratic participation, creating new models through deliberative processes. It aims to mitigate bias in AI systems and ensure privacy while promoting meaningful civic engagement.

Industrial

The projects are creating valuable tools for various professionals, especially in technology. Expertise in AI and software development is key for developing online discussion platforms. There are opportunities for technology companies to provide services related to platform design and benefit from project results.

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